

DEVELOPING SELF-RENEWAL CAPACITY SCALE BASED ON PACE MODEL

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Abstract

Self-Renewal Capacity in learning can improve your own potential. Through Self-Renewal Capacity, students can increase the capacity/performance in the study, include: exploitation, exploration, absorption, integration, and leadership. One of models that can improve the Self-Renewal Capacity is PACE. PACE is one of models based on constructivist learning that has phase: Projects, Activities, Cooperative learning and Exercise. To determine self-renewal capacity, developed Self-Renewal Capacity Scale based on PACE Model by development research.

Keywords: *Self-Renewal Capacity, PACE Model*

INTRODUCTION

Math materials for college is difficult to study because the material presented is more abstract. An example is Statistics Mathematics Course. Student have difficulty in learning Mathematical Statistics material (Marron, 1999), applying mathematical techniques in the field of statistics (Petocz & Smith, 2007), and in the process of mathematical proofs (Petocz & Smith, 2007). Based on the results of interviews with several students at one university in Jakarta that they rarely less self-reflection and exploration in learning. The capacity of a person to always improve their work through study and empirical reflection is called Self-Renewal Capacity (Bustanul, 2011).

Self-Renewal Capacity must be improved because students need to improve their performance and to reflect that the next performance will be better. They will be motivated to move forward, always explore, and assimilate even accommodation in the cognitive structure of the information obtained.

To improve the Self-Renewal Capacity of students in Mathematical statistics Course, the lecturer should give the opportunity to students to be active in learning and to construct the concepts to their own ability.

One of the models that embrace constructivist learning theory is the PACE model. PACE model developed by Lee (1999) for learning statistics which stands for Project, Activity, Cooperative learning and Exercise. Students are taught by the PACE model far more active in learning through class discussion (Lee, 1999). To know the Self-Renewal Capacity student, developed the Self-Renewal Capacity Scale based on the PACE model.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Self-Renewal Capacity

Self-Renewal Capacity concept was first presented by Sotarauta and Stahle (Saarivirta, 2007). According Sotarauta (Saarivirta, 2007), the Self-Renewal Capacity is a process that deliberately planned for the future and the process of adaptation. Self-Renewal Capacity can be seen as the ability intended for personal renewal, organization or even resources. Stahle (Saarivirta, 2007) sees the Self-Renewal Capacity as the overall capacity of an individual or organization to capture the changes that shaped the strategy, operations and knowledge, and to manage information, knowledge and innovation. Sotarauta (Saarivirta, 2007) have set five indicators Self-Renewal Capacity. The fifth

indicator is the exploitation, exploration, absorption, Integration, and Leadership.

Based on the description above, the Self-Renewal Capacity in this study is the capacity to always improve work through learning and self-reflection cover exploitation, exploration, absorption, integration, and leadership.

PACE Model

PACE model developed by Lee (1999) for learning a statistic which is an abbreviation of Project, Activity (Activity), cooperative learning (Cooperative Learning) and exercise (Exercise). Students are taught by the PACE model far more active through class discussion (Lee, 1999).

The project is an important component of the PACE model. Laviatan (2008) says that the project is an innovative form of learning that emphasizes the complex activities to solve problems based on inquiry activities. Project activities in the form of groups. They can choose their own topics. They were asked to find solutions to the problems of his choice. They should make a report of the project. In this project, students are required to be active, critical and creative. Through the project, students better understand the concepts and can improve retention and can explore mathematical abilities, both cognitive and affective abilities.

The aim of Activity in PACE model is to introduce students to information or new concepts by giving a task in the form of Activity Worksheet. Activity Worksheet is one form of the Student Worksheet to learn the material. Through Activity Worksheet, students are given the opportunity to find their own concepts that will be learned.

Cooperative learning in the PACE model is implemented in the classroom. In the study, students work in groups and discussions to find solutions of the problem in the Discussion Worksheet. Discussion Worksheet is a form of the Student Worksheet too to learn the

material. Through Worksheet discussion, students had the opportunity to present the findings obtained during the discussion. During the discussion, students exchange ideas in order to get a correct understanding of the concept.

The purpose of exercise in the PACE model is to reinforce the concepts that have been constructed on activities and cooperative learning. This exercise is given to students in the form of additional duties in Exercise Worksheet. Through Exercise Worksheet, students can understand the material better. Phase exercises related to reflection, that is to re-examine the results and the process (Polya, 1981).

Based on description above, the PACE model in this study is a model of learning based on constructivism which has a phase: Projects, Activities, and cooperative learning exercises using Worksheet Students in the learning process.

METHOD

This study is a research on the development of Self-Renewal Capacity scale based on PACE model. The research was conducted in Mathematics Education Program, University of Indraprasta PGRI Jakarta. This development research is modified from Borg & Gall models (1983). The stages/phases of the modified model is:

- 1) Theoretical review and exploration.
- 2) Arrange of Self-Renewal Capacity Scale.
- 3) The expert validation of the Self-Renewal Capacity Scale has been arranged. Validation include validation of content and face. Validators are 7 people in the field, namely: a Doctor of statistics, 3 Master of Mathematics who are studying in Doctoral Program, and 3 Master of Mathematic Education who are studying in Doctoral Program. The results of validation

test calculated using software of SPSS Statistics 20.

- 4) Make revisions based on suggestions from the validator.
- 5) Try Out of Self-Renewal Capacity to students of Mathematics Education Program, University of Indraprasta PGRI Jakarta to find out the validity and reliability of the instrument. The results of try out calculated using software of SPSS Statistics 20.

RESULT

Arrange of Self-Renewal Capacity Scale

After reviewing the literature and exploration of the various sources of the Self-Renewal Capacity and its indicators, then obtained sub-indicators of Self-Renewal Capacity. Then developed into statements. Sub-indicators of the Self-Renewal Capacity indicators are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Indicators and Sub-indicators of Self-Renewal Capacity

No.	Indicator	Sub Indicator
1	Exploitation	Utilizing the information for a particular purpose
		Utilizing the potential in yourself
2	Exploration	Have creative ideas
		Making generalizations
		prove
		representing
		Have a high curiosity to new something
3	Absorption	Adaptation
4	Integration	Respect for others
		Prioritize common interests
		Being able to control himself against conflict
5	Leadership	Working hard to solve the problem
		Have a strong motivation from yourself
		Have skills in communicating
		Take decisions in solving problems
		be responsible
		thorough

The expert validation

Validation include validation of content and face. The indicators are as follows:

- 1) The indicator of content validation is the statement in accordance with the indicators and sub-indicators.
- 2) The indicator of face validation is a good statement; not ambiguity; using a common language; and easy to understand.

Experts assess instrument of Self-Renewal Capacity scale to write the number "1" if the statement is valid, and "0" if it is not valid. The results of the face and content validity by a validator is processed using the Cochran Q-statistic. The results are as follows:

Table 2 Result of Face Validity

Test Statistics

<i>N</i>	46
<i>Cochran's Q</i>	5.000 ^a
<i>df</i>	6
<i>Asymp. Sig.</i>	.544

^a. 1 is treated as a success.

Table 3 Result of Content Validity

Test Statistics

<i>N</i>	46
<i>Cochran's Q</i>	8.667 ^a
<i>df</i>	6
<i>Asymp. Sig.</i>	.193

^a. 1 is treated as a success.

Based on the table above shows that, Asymp. Sig. more than the value of alpha (5%). This means that experts have considered the uniform of the face and content validity of the Self-Renewal Capacity Scale. The next step is to revise based on the advice of experts.

Try Out of Self-Renewal Capacity to students of Mathematics Education Program, University of Indraprasta PGRI Jakarta

To determine the validity and reliability of the Self-Renewal Capacity Scale, this instrument is tested to 40 students. Scores from the results of test converted using the MSI software. Furthermore, the results of score conversion processed using the software of SPSS Statistics 20. The results are as follows:

Table 4 Result of Validity Test

	Corrected Item-Total Correlation
VAR00001	.569
VAR00002	-.167
VAR00003	.398
VAR00004	.523
VAR00005	.444
VAR00006	.405
VAR00007	.167
VAR00008	.334
VAR00009	.399
VAR00010	.374
VAR00011	.407
VAR00012	.313
VAR00013	.485
VAR00014	.640
VAR00015	.392
VAR00016	.372
VAR00017	.457
VAR00018	.099
VAR00019	.488
VAR00020	.375
VAR00021	.359
VAR00022	.155
VAR00023	-.060
VAR00024	.476
VAR00025	.418
VAR00026	.053
VAR00027	.382
VAR00028	.384
VAR00029	.403
VAR00030	.029
VAR00031	.440
VAR00032	.584
VAR00033	.449
VAR00034	.511
VAR00035	.625
VAR00036	.477
VAR00037	.577
VAR00038	.593
VAR00039	.347
VAR00040	.044
VAR00041	.335
VAR00042	.425
VAR00043	.608
VAR00044	.068
VAR00045	.363
VAR00046	.577

Table 5 Results of Reliability Test

<i>Reliability Statistics</i>	
<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
.873	46

To determine the reliability of the Self-Renewal Capacity Scale can be seen from the value of Cronbach's Alpha, and then compared with the r product moment. For alpha 5% and $df = n-1 = 39$ obtained $r_{table} = 0.316$. If the value of Cronbach's Alpha $> r_{table}$, it can be said the scale is reliable. This scale is reliable because the value of the Cronbach's Alpha (0.873) $> r_{table}$ (0,316).

To know about the validity of the Self-Renewal Capacity Scale, can be seen from the correlation value of each item statement (Corrected Item-Total Correlation), then compared with the r product moment. For alpha 5% and $df = n-1 = 39$ obtained $r_{table} = 0.316$. If the Corrected Item-Total Correlation $> r_{table}$, then the statement is valid. So, the statement is not valid according to Table 4 is No. 2, 7, 18, 22, 23, 26, 30, 40, and 44, in order to obtain 37 points from 46 points scale Self-Renewal Capacity is valid and reliable. It is the final instrument and can be used for further research.

CONCLUSION

Self-Renewal Capacity Scale is based on PACE model has been developed to obtain 37-point declaration is valid and reliable. It can be used for further research, which is to measure the improvement or attainment Self-Renewal Capacity through the PACE model.

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